

EFFECT OF SIT-AT-HOME ON ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT IN ENUGU STATE

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Abstract

The sit-at-home order imposed by an organization, the Indigenous People of Biafra (IPOB), has become a recurring word among the dwellers in Enugu State within the Southeastern part of Nigeria and as such, there is virtually non-movement of persons on specified days. Every Monday since mid-2021 has been marked as a non-movement day in the region pending the release of its leader, Mazi Nnamdi Kanu, from detention. With a sample of 1000 respondents in a survey research design, this study adopted descriptive techniques to examine the effects of sit-at-home on economic development in Enugu State in the year 2022. The results, supported by both descriptive statistics outcome and hypothesis test, revealed that economic development was negatively affected by the IPOB sit-at-home order. This study recommends that government should reach an agreement with the IPOB hierarchy to restore a sound business environment for the expected level of investment inflow in the Southeast region and Enugu State in particular.

1.1 Introduction

Enugu State, located in the Southeastern part of Nigeria, has observed several sit-at-home orders as a way of protest for the release of IPOB's leader, Mazi Nnamdi Kanu (Aytogo, 2021). The sit-at-home orders are usually observed on Mondays and other days of the week Nnamdi Kanu is to appear before a court of competent jurisdiction (Emeruwa, 2021). Economic activities are halted on days the orders are to be observed as no one is allowed to carry out any transaction intra and inter States. Anyone found flouting the orders is either killed or

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attacked to submission (Ugwu, 2022). The sit-at-home orders are binding on the five States (Ebonyi, Enugu, Anambra, Imo and Abia States) in the Southeastern part of Nigeria and partially in some States in the South-South (Delta, Rivers) (Ayitogo, 2021). The Southeastern part of the country and some States in the above geopolitical zones where these orders are binding are self-considered to belong to the Indigenous People of Biafra (IPOB) (Ugwu, 2021). Virtually, the sit-at-home orders invariably have effect on all geopolitical zones in Nigeria. This is because on the days the orders are to be observed, movements are restricted into the Southeastern States from other geopolitical zones of the country.

According to Esho (2022), IPOB was formed in 2012 by Mazi Nnamdi Kanu over perceived excessive wield and abuse of power by the Nigerian State which they deemed tyrannical and indirectly coercive on the Igbo nation. In the same vein, the IPOB was formed as a movement against corruption and marginalization of the Igbo nation (Okafor, 2017). Consequently, the quest for independence of the Biafrans (Igbos) from Nigerian Government became evident and orchestrated by various activities they deemed fit, irrespective of their inimical effects on the entire economy. One of the strategies adopted to gain their quest for freedom was several media attacks on the Nigerian Government by the IPOB hierarchy. In view of this, the Nigerian Government deemed the series of attacks as breaches to national peaceful coexistence (Ugwu, 2022).

Consequently on 19th of October 2015, Nnamdi Kanu was arrested through concerted efforts from security operatives, thereafter charged for sedition, ethnic incitement and treasonable felony (Emeruwa, 2021). The arrest birthed a number of experiences across major cities in the Eastern part of Nigeria. For example, on the 2nd of December 2015, major cities in Anambra State especially in Onitsha, parts of Aba, Umuahia, and Enugu States recorded high rate of protests, riots, and police clashes. The experiences led to the death and injury of massive numbers of youths (Ayitogo, 2021). Sequel to a number of agitations from members of the public, Nnamdi Kanu was later bailed.

Following series of events by the Nigerian security operatives such as the 'operation python dance', Nnamdi Kanu left Nigeria to the UK on the grounds that his life was threatened (Ugwu, 2022). In the UK, he kept using the media to attack the Nigerian Government under the leadership of President Muhammad Buhari. The situation worsened so much, that in June 2021, Kanu was arrested by the Nigerian Government in Kenya and brought back to the country (Emeruwa, 2021). He was re-arraigned on charges of treasonable felony over his agitation for the separatist Republic of Biafra. On July 30th, 2021, Emma Powerful, the IPOB spokesperson declared that every Monday starting from August 9, 2021 would be a sit-at-home, although the orders are annually observed prior to this time to remember those who lost their lives in the Nigeria-Biafra war (Esho, 2022). This form of protest would continue till Nnamdi Kanu is released from the custody of the Department of State Security. Hence, from the foregoing, it can be deduced that the intent of the creator of this order was to use it as a means of peaceful protest to ensure the release of Mazi Nnamdi Kanu and secure the political freedom of the people of Biafra.

1.2 Statement of the problems

The frequency of the sit-at-home order has become a thorn in the flesh of the people as it affects their daily living and has triggered a backlash and retrogression to the economy of the eastern region of Nigeria. The effect of the order is felt in the economic, social, educational, and other sectors of the economy of Enugu State. The notion that the sit-at-home order is ruining the economy of Enugu State is the drive of this study. Hence, this seminar work is poised to investigate the extent the sit-at-home order has affected the development of Enugu State in the year 2022.

1.3 Objectives of the Study

- i. To determine the effect of sit-at-home orders on the economic development in Enugu State in the year 2022.

- ii. To ascertain the inimical damage caused by sit-at-home orders on Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) in Enugu State in the year 2022.
- iii. To know the impact of the sit-at-home order on social infrastructure in Enugu State in the year 2022.

1.4 Statement of Hypotheses

H1: Sit-at-home order does not have a significant relationship with economic development

H2: Sit-at-home order does not have a significant relationship with foreign direct investment

H3: Sit-at-home order does not have a significant relationship with social infrastructures

Review of Related Literature

2.1 Conceptual Literature

Economic activities are disrupted on days the sit-at-home orders are observed in Enugu State of Nigeria because productive assets and resources are placed on hold (Okeoma, 2021). This is accompanied by loss of lives and properties, especially by those who share contrary opinions with the IPOB hierarchy. Vaskov, Pienknagura, and Ricci (2021) revealed in their study that restrictions of people's movement cripple economic activities especially in countries with low economic development. Okafor (2022) submitted that social unrest in Nigeria has resulted to cumulative decline in GDP from 2011 to 2015. Odili (2021) remarked that the sit-at-home order has caused the economy of the Southeast a massive decline in GDP relative to other geopolitical zones in the country. Also, Azeez (2022) quoted Simon Ekpa that the sit-at-home order has made Nigeria governments lose estimated revenue worth more than \$1 billion on weekly basis.

Generally, social unrest is inimical to economic development in any economy of the world. In Nigeria for example, the recent EndSARS demonstration caused series of economic downturn in major States of Nigeria. The Lagos Chamber of Commerce and Industry (LCCI) (2020) highlighted that the EndSARS demonstration which lasted for twelve days resulted in the loss of N700 billion in revenue to the Nigerian government. In the same vein, the Lekki toll gate closure during the days of the EndSARS forced the government of Lagos State to lose N234 million in revenue (Emenike, 2020). SB Morgan surveyed 180 business owners after the EndSARS demonstration, 91% of business owners accepted that their businesses were grossly affected, 98% agreed that they lost both customers and revenue, 43% of respondents agreed they were looted to the tune of more than N1 million worth of resources and 26% agreed they lost between N500,000 to N1,000,000 during the protest (Odutola, 2021). The conclusion from the report revealed that business owners were subjected to inability of settling debts, destruction and looting of resources, and the fear of business activities picking up due to business slowdown.

Onime (2018) submitted that social unrest in Nigeria such as the activities of Boko-Haram, IPOB, Niger-Delta Militants, Herdsmen and kidnapping have at various times crumbled the economy of Nigeria. He further noted that, violent agitation of these groups for both human and non-human resource control have resulted in loss of lives, oil theft and bunkering, pipe vandalism, displacement of people from their ancestral homes and nation-wide hunger among others. The sit-at-home order, as one of the many social unrests in Nigeria from economic point of view, is not healthy for the economy of South-Eastern Nigeria and beyond.

Sit-At-Home Order and Foreign Direct Investment

The growth of the economy of Southeastern Nigeria largely depends on the accelerating and stimulating strength of Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) (Odili, 2020). The influx of FDI to any region has similar economic outcome such as a boost in transfer of technology, domestic production, financial capital development, job creation and economic development among others (Bitar, Hamadeh, and Khoueiri, 2019). Despite the relevance of FDI to the economy of Southeast, the sit-at-home order has, to a large extent, impeded the flow of FDI to the region.

As emphasized by the US Department of State (2020), the problem of insecurity threatens investors resolve to make investment decisions in Nigeria. The restriction of movement on Mondays has added to the list of security challenges bedeviling Nigeria; anyone who flouts the order may eventually lose his/her life and properties. Unscrupulous elements utilize sit-at-home days to perpetrate evils such as kidnapping for ransom, violent conducts of different magnitude and terrorist attacks on anyone who fall prey. FDI is attracted in business environments devoid of low confidence and alarming rate of uncertainties, hence the sit-at-home order is not a promoter of FDI in the eastern region of the country (Vaskov, Pienknagura, and Ricci, 2021). By implication, the sit-at-home order stifles FDI, promotes fear and disillusionment to businesses and tourism.

According to Odili (2021), no investor would be proud to invest in business environments where confidence of investment protection is grossly low. After a careful examination of myriads of outcomes and tensions associated with the sit-at-home orders, foreign investors would undoubtedly be afraid to invest in such volatile business environments. Onyebuchi (2018) concurred to the above sentiment when he submitted that due to social unrests in Nigeria, greater number of foreign investors have left Nigeria for other nations with stable business environment. UNCTAD report cited in Onyebuchi (2018) established that from 2007-2009, Nigeria was among the 40 most viable and attractive economies for FDI, however series of social unrests in the country has changed the trajectory. The 2018 UNCTAD report revealed that Nigeria's FDI inflow declined by 21% while capital flight trended up by 8% (Dajo and Akor, 2022). The decline in FDI is attributable to series of social unrests in Nigeria where sit-at-home order has added to existing long list (Esho, 2022).

Sit-At-Home Order and Social Infrastructure

A major catalyst of economic development in developing countries is adequate availability of social infrastructure. Such infrastructural facilities like roads, railways, health centres, adequate electrical energy among others can stimulate the transformation of the society. Nigeria's per-capita growth performance has 1% growth as a result of net contribution from infrastructural roles to the economy (African Infrastructure Country Diagnostic, 2011). Hence, infrastructure is an agent of socio-economic development. The African Infrastructure Country Diagnostic (2011) estimated that Nigeria needs 12% of her GDP or USD14.2 billion to address infrastructural gaps over next few decades. The above estimate may not be enough to address infrastructural gaps owing to the increasing social unrests prevalent in all regions of the country.

According to Ugwu (2022), social infrastructure requires huge financial investment in terms of both maintenance and construction. However, nefarious activities of unscrupulous elements under the guise of IPOB and several other criminal elements across the South-eastern Nigeria have continuously attacked social infrastructure, hence cascading negative effects on economic growth and development of the region. Renn, Jovanovich and Schroter (2011) submitted in their work that social unrest of whatever magnitude cause damages to social utilities. Similar to the IPOB sit-at-home orders, activities of Boko-Haram, Herdsmen, Niger-Delta Militants, kidnappers, religious and ethnic conflicts among others have caused destabilization to critical social infrastructures that took many years to build (Dajo and Akor, 2022).

A quick look at the impact of various social unrests in Nigeria shows that 75% of sanitation and water infrastructure has been destroyed due to incessant conflict in the Northeast (UNDP, 2017). In the same vein, UNICEF (2017) mentioned that more than 496 classrooms have been destroyed beyond repair while 1392 classrooms were damaged albeit, repairable in the Northeast. According to Olasupo (2020), about 205 major national security facilities, corporate and private facilities were damaged in the 2020 EndSARS protests. Olasupo further reported that 71 public warehouses and 248 private businesses in 13 States were destroyed during the protest. As reported by Okeoma (2021), the government of Nigeria claimed that the paramilitary wing of IPOB, known as Eastern Security Network (ESN), destroyed eighteen INEC offices and a hundred and sixty-four

security facilities in the Southeastern part of the country. These arguments show that all forms of social unrests disrupt social infrastructure to the detriment of economic growth and development.

2.2 Theoretical Framework

Frustration/Aggression Theory

The theory was developed in 1939 by John Dollard and colleagues, albeit refined in 1962 by Berkowitz and Aubrey (Dajo and Akor, 2022). The theory was developed for typical explanation of violent criminal behavior in conjunction with social unrests and disturbances as a quest to achieve pressing needs from necessary authorities (Odoma and Akor, 2019). According to Dajo and Akor (2022), frustration arises when there is an unwanted interference between a goal and response which can lead to aggression. Based on the above sentiment, aggression is a resultant outcome when attempts to achieve certain goals are blocked or impeded, resulting in frustration. According to Igwe (2011), the inability to confront the source of impediment to achieving goals, subjects the aggrieved party into directing their frustration at innocent targets.

Every government is responsible for the provision of conducive social, economic and political environment upon which her citizens can successfully thrive. In practice, such environment is not easily found. For instance, on annual basis, higher institutions in Nigeria release thousands of graduates into the labour market only to be frustrated with little or no paid employment jobs (Oduma and Akor, 2019). Coupled with accumulated existing challenges, these graduates are faced with bleak futures leaving them with no other option than frustration. These experiences explain the reason behind series of civil unrests such as ethnic, religious, and communal conflicts often experienced since Nigeria returned to civil administration in 1999. In the context of the IPOB, they claimed to be frustrated of all sorts of social ill meted on them by the Nigerian government. Such social ill is majorly claimed to be marginalization of the Igbos in the social, political and economic stream of the country. On a general note, Faminu (2021) highlighted that between 2020 and 2021, more than 2,000 lives have been lost in Nigeria largely because of the activities of Boko Haram, Herdsmen, Niger-Delta militants, the Oduduwa groups, the recent EndSARS protests and the on-going IPOB sit-at-home order enforced by the Eastern Security Network (ESN). These activities cannot be said to be unconnected with bottled up anger and frustrations.

The relevance of Frustration/Aggression theory to this study is not unconnected to the fact that the IPOB conceive the Nigerian government as the main clogging body to the actualization of the independence of Biafra. The IPOB claim to be frustrated with government administration in Nigeria, where they are deprived equal representation in various agencies and parastatals as well as the seat of presidency. Mazi Nnamdi Kanu was arrested and detained for his activities which is not far from frustration albeit, the Nigerian government deem his activities inimical to the peaceful co-existence of the nation. The efforts to get Nnamdi Kanu released proved abortive, hence more frustrations to the IPOB members. This gave birth to the sit-at-home orders being observed in the Southeastern part of Nigeria. The series of social unrests experienced in Nigeria is as a result of bottled-up anger and frustration inherent in Nigeria. The alarming rate of poverty, police brutality, high level of insecurity and marginalization are some of the by-products frustrating the youths in the country's social, political economic environment. Youths and the aged see Nigerian government as a failed administration, hence the loss of trust. Social unrest is a common occurrence at the slightest provocation in the country, resulting in attacks on social infrastructure, unhealthy business environment for domestic and FDI and ultimately consistent decline of economic growth.

2.3 Empirical Framework

Owoeye, Ezeanya, and Obiegbunam (2022) examined the impact of IPOB's Monday sit-at-home order on Nigeria's political economy (socio-political and economic activity). The paper is a qualitative descriptive survey. The data was analyzed thematically with logical reasoning, with Tacoltt Parsons and David Easton's systems theory analysis serving as a theoretical guide. The study's findings revealed that IPOB's Monday sit-at-home has

hurt Southeastern Nigeria's economic operations. In light of the foregoing, the study recommended, among other things, that the issue of Mazi Nnamdi Kanu, the leader of IPOB, be resolved as soon as possible, since the Monday sit-at-home order was a strategy to persuade the Federal Government to release IPOB's leader, Mazi Nnamdi Kanu, from detention.

A study was carried out by Chukwudi, Gberevbie, Abasilim, and Imhonopi (2019) on IPOB's demand for self-determination and Nigeria's response: Implications for political stability. The study investigates IPOB agitation techniques and the Nigerian government's response to IPOB agitators, as well as the implications for political stability. The study used a survey research approach, with a sample size of 385 members of the IPOB taken from a sample size determination table. One of the methods used to obtain data from the respondents was an in-depth interview. The Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) was used to analyze the data collected. The investigations revealed that the government has been using unwarranted force through its agents. It was recommended among others that government should employ the carrot approach instead of the stick approach in dealing with IPOB members.

Gap in Literature

More efforts should be made by researchers on the number of lives lost during the sit-at-home order in Enugu State and also to unearth businesses that closed down due to the inability to make sales and gain profit during the period of sit-at-home.

3. Methodology

The study adopted an online survey design which allowed the collection of primary data through the use of online questionnaires. World Population Review (2022) estimates the population of the Enugu State at 847,000 people. These people constituted the population of the study. However, despite the large number of the study population, 1648 persons were sampled for this study cutting across both individuals and business executives. The choice of the sample size is backed by Conroy (2018) who submitted that irrespective of how large a study population is, a sample size above 1648 does not add much to data accuracy but extra time and more cost. The study adopted an online survey design which allowed the collection of primary data through the use of online questionnaires. The data generated for the study were subjected to statistical analysis using Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS). Statistical tools of percentages, mean and standard deviation were employed for the description section while the hypotheses were tested with the help of the Chi-Square statistical tool.

Taro Yamane Formula (1967) to determine the sample size, resulting in a sample size of 824 respondents instead of the targeted 1648;

$$n = N / (1 + N(e)^2) \text{ where;}$$

n signifies the sample size

N signifies the population under study (1,648)

e signifies the margin error (2.5%)

4. Data Presentation and Analyses

Of the 1648 expected responses, 824 persons responded to the questionnaire and it gives a response rate of 82.4%. The demographic analysis of respondents is tabulated below:

Descriptive Statistics of Results

Respondents' opinions are analyzed in this section with the view of making inferences using the mean and standard deviation (std.) of responses. The mean and std. benchmarks are 3.0 and 1.5 respectively on a rated opinion Likert scale of 1-5 as employed in Pornel (2009). This implies that mean values equal to or above the benchmark are considered to be positive and significant in explaining the variables and vice-versa. Also, any std. value equal or above the benchmark was regarded to have wide deviation from the mean and be misleading.

Table 4.2.1: Mean rating of respondents on the effect of sit-at-home order on economic development of Enugu state.

S/N	ITEM STATEMENT	\bar{X}	S	Decision
1	Sit-at-home order disrupts productive assets in Enugu State	3.95	0.95	A
2	Sit-at-home order reduces income level of households	3.44	0.97	A
3	Sit-at-home order exposes human resources to injury and death	3.81	0.98	A
4	Sit-at-home order reduces educational quality and standard of living.	3.22	0.80	A
5	Sit-at-home order reduces productive work hours in the region	3.19	0.95	A
6	Sit-at-home order reduces total economic output in the region	3.55	1.18	A

Keys:- \bar{X} mean, S- standard deviation, A-accepted/ Agreed

As revealed in table 4.2.1, the items have mean range between 3.19 and 3.95, hence they were all more than the cut-off mean of 3.0. This implies that all the items are significant in explaining the effect of sit-at-home order on economic development of Enugu State. Similarly, it was revealed that none of the mean responses have wide deviation from each other since their standard are at close range to each other.

Table 4.2.2: Mean rating of respondents on the effect of sit-at-home order on foreign direct investment in Enugu state

S/N	ITEM STATEMENT	\bar{X}	S	Decision
1	Sit-at-home order disrupts technological transfer through FDI inflow	3.13	1.01	A
2	Sit-at-home order disrupts FDI through reduced market size	3.21	0.91	A
3	Sit-at-home order reduces FDI through macroeconomic instabilities	3.96	0.87	A
4	Sit-at-home order affects FDI through distortion in GDP growth rate	3.28	0.92	A
5	Sit-at-home order disrupts abilities of businesses to repatriate profits	3.49	0.99	A
6	Sit-at-home order disrupts business regulatory environment	3.25	1.08	A

Keys:- \bar{X} mean, S- standard deviation, A-accepted/ Agreed

In table 4.2.2, the items have mean range between 3.13 and 3.96, hence they were all more than the cut-off mean of 3.0. This implies that all the items are significant in explaining the effect of sit-at-home order on FDI in Enugu

State. Similarly, it was revealed that none of the mean responses have wide deviation from each other since their standard are at close range to each other.

Table 4.2.3: Mean rating of respondents on the effect of sit-at-home order on social infrastructure in Enugu State

S/N	ITEM STATEMENT	\bar{X}	S	Decision
1	The order reduces quality services of educational facilities	3.07	0.91	A
2	The order affects quality services of medical facilities	3.28	0.96	A
3	The order reduces sanitation on the social environment	3.16	0.77	A
4	Sit-at-home order increases pressure on housing facilities	3.28	0.94	A
5	Sit-at-home order increases pressure on water facilities	3.49	0.96	A
6	Sit-at-home order increases pressure on power infrastructure	3.25	0.93	A

Keys:- mean, S- standard deviation, A-accepted/ Agreed

In table 4.2.3 above, the items have mean range between 3.07 and 3.49, hence they were all more than the cut-off mean of 3.0. This implies that all the items are significant in explaining the effect of sit-at-home order on social infrastructure in Enugu State. Similarly, it was revealed that none of the mean responses have wide deviation from each other since their standard are at close range to each other.

4.3 Test of Hypotheses

The statement of hypothesis is rejected if calculated X^2 is higher than tabulated X^2 , otherwise it should be accepted.

H0₁: Sit-at-home order does not have significant relationship with economic growth

$$D.F = (C-1)(R-1) = (3-1) (6-1) = 2 \times 5 = 10$$

X^2 tab for 10 D.F. at 0.05 level of significance = 18.31

The value of chi-square calculated is 18.06 while the table value is 18.31 at 5% significance level. The calculated chi-square is less than the tabulated, hence the null hypothesis is accepted and concludes that sit-at-home has negative significant relationship and impact on economic growth in Enugu State.

H0₂: Sit-at-home order does not have significant relationship with foreign direct investment

$$D.F = (C-1)(R-1) = (3-1) (6-1) = 2 \times 5 = 10$$

X^2 tab for 10 D.F. at 0.05 level of significance = 18.31

The value of chi-square calculated is 17.96 while the table value is 18.31 at 5% significance level. The calculated chi-square is less than the tabulated, hence the null hypothesis is accepted and concludes that sit-at-home has negative significant relationship and impact on FDI in Enugu State.

H0₃: Sit-at-home order does not have significant relationship with social infrastructures

$$D.F = (C-1)(R-1) = (3-1) (6-1) = 2 \times 5 = 10$$

X^2 tab for 10 D.F. at 0.05 level of significance = 18.31

The value of chi-square calculated is 18.27 while the table value is 18.31 at 5% significance level. The calculated chi-square is less than the tabulated, hence the null hypothesis is accepted and concludes that sit-at-home has negative significant relationship and impact on social infrastructure in Enugu State.

4.4 Discussion of Findings

From the first objective of the study with emphasis on the effects of sit-at-home order on economic development of Enugu state, it was revealed that economic development is negatively affected by the IPOB sit-at-home order. The result was supported by both descriptive statistics outcome and test of hypothesis. Specifically, variables such as productive assets, household's income level, educational quality, productive work hours, human resources output and total economic output were affected by the sit-at-home order in Enugu State. By implication, any order restricting people going about their daily businesses is inimical to economic health of such region. The study findings is in line with the findings of Vaskov, Pienknagura, and Ricci (2021) who established that social unrests have negative effect on economic activities of mostly developing countries. Similarly, Onime (2018) and Dajo and Akor (2022) established such result in their studies.

The result for the second objective revealed that sit-at-home order negatively impacted foreign direct investment (FDI) as evident in both the descriptive statistics and test of hypothesis. In the result presentation, it was revealed that technology transfer through FDI inflow, size of the market, economic stability, GDP growth rate, repatriation of business profits and business regulatory environment were all affected by the sit-at-home order. The effect of the order on the above variables directly and indirectly affects FDI as the confidence to invest are punctured by unfavourable business environment. The above findings is in conformity with Onyebuchi (2018) who established that FDI does not thrive in uncertain business environment. Dajo and Akor (2022) who cited UNCTAD World investment Report (2018) and Adenyuma and Onyeche (2019) revealed that series of social unrests in Nigeria decreased FDI by 21% and capital flight increased by 8%.

In justifying the third objective of the study, it was revealed that sit-at-home order has negative impact on social infrastructure in Enugu State. The descriptive statistics and test of hypothesis confirmed the above result. The study revealed that social infrastructures such as educational facilities, medical facilities, sanitation on the social environment, housing facilities and water facilities were all negatively affected by the sit-at-home order. The above result is synonymous with reports from UNICEF (2017) that social unrests in Northern part of Nigeria have caused great destruction to social infrastructure in the region. Similarly, Olasupo (2020) revealed that EndSARs protests and activities of the IPOB have caused massive negative pressure on social infrastructure in the country.

5.1 Summary of Findings

In table 1, the mean and std. benchmarks are 3.0 and 1.5 respectively on rated opinion likert scale of 1-5 as employed in Pornel (2009). This implies that mean values equal or above the benchmark is considered to be positive and significant in explaining the variables and vice-versa.

As revealed in table 4.2.1, the items have mean range between 3.19 and 3.95, hence they were all more than the cut-off mean of 3.0. This implies that all the items are significant in explaining the effect of sit-at-home order on economic development of Enugu State.

In table 4.2.2, the items have mean range between 3.13 and 3.96, hence they were all more than the cut-off mean of 3.0. This implies that all the items are significant in explaining the effect of sit-at-home order on FDI in Enugu State.

And lastly in table 4.2.3, the items have mean range between 3.07 and 3.49, hence they were all more than the cut-off mean of 3.0. This implies that all the items are significant in explaining the effect of sit-at-home order on social infrastructure in Enugu State.

5.2 Conclusion

The study has been able to establish negative effects and relationships amongst sit-at-home order, economic development, foreign direct investment and social infrastructure. The study revealed that the sit-at-home order affects FDI and social infrastructure hence it has a negative moderating effect on economic development in the Enugu State.

5.3 Recommendations

Based on these findings, the following recommendations are made:

- The government should take more proactive measure to instill order in Enugu State and other Southeastern part of Nigeria to avoid unlawful restrictions inimical to economic activities.
- The government should come to terms of agreement with the IPOB hierarchy to restore sound business environment for expected level of FDI inflow in the Enugu State.
- The government should subject security operatives to more advanced trainings to curtail ill acts of unscrupulous elements bent on damaging social infrastructures in the Enugu State.

5.4 Contribution to Knowledge

The effect of mandatory closure of markets and restriction of movement on Mondays by IPOB and its economic implications in Enugu State, Nigeria was examined. It was exposed that the order with total compliance in the state has a negative economic implication on not only the state but the country at large. The study concludes that the sit-at-home order on Mondays by IPOB in the Enugu state of the country has brought economic hardship to the state. The research is significant in providing new statistical and empirical data for Government and Security agents to prioritize resolving the concerns of IPOB and hence bringing an end to the Sit at Home order in Southeastern Nigeria and Enugu in particular.

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